

DIFFERENT TYPES OF MODERN FOOTBALL

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Annotation: The article deals with significant point about football, its rules and physical requirements. In addition to this, some new forms of football which are famous around the world as a football game and their difference to each other are highlighted.

Key words: *football match, clamor, slide tackle, spun, footballing culture, international competition, Beach soccer, Swamp Football.*

Football is the most liked sport by people all over the world, no doubt about it. Baseball is liked by many people in the USA, Europe, and some parts of Asia, but American Football is only played in the USA. Many people in the UK and countries that used to be British colonies like to play cricket. Football is a game that people play everywhere in the world. There are 211 countries that are part of FIFA. They are split into six regions: CONCACAF, UEFA, CONMEBOL, CAF, AFC, and OFC. This means that every country on every continent can play in a FIFA World Cup qualifying match. Football is called "The Beautiful Game" because it is really enjoyable to watch. Football looks nice to watch. Watching a football game is exciting because of the loud fans, the cheering, the intense feelings, the grassy field, and all the other things happening. Watching a perfect slide tackle, a great freekick, or an amazing goal to the top corner is really nice. This game is fun to watch for a specific reason.

There are no physical requirements for playing football. Other sports, such as basketball and American football, have specific physical requirements, such as being very tall and having a powerful physique[1]. You don't have to be really fit to play football. Lionel Messi is one of the best footballers in the world, but he is quite short at about 1.70 meters. In football, boys and girls can play together. Both boys and girls play by the same rules in the game. The Women's World Cup is a big sports event and one of the most important women's sports events ever. People play different kinds of football all over the world. The Neymar Jr's Five tournament is a new game inspired by football, which is not the first time this has happened. A new and fun soccer tournament is coming up. It will challenge the best players from around the world to show off their skills. The best teams from different countries can compete against each other in a big competition in Brazil. This new contest was created from football. In the past, there were many games that became popular and competitive on their own.

Futsal- The game has roots in South America and it's considered an important part of the region's footballing culture[2]. Futsal, which is derived from the Spanish name, 'futbol sala', which means room football, first originated in the inner cities of South America in the mid-1930s. An Argentinian coach named Juan Carlos Ceriani reportedly conjured the idea after finding a need to practice football indoors in order to avoid rain-soaked pitches. The idea worked and Futsal caught on like wildfire across the world. Mini leagues were formed in the early 50s and the first reported international competition – the Confederacion Sudamericana de Futbol de Salon, took place in 1965. Today Futsal forms an integral part of football and it has helped a number of champions such as Pele and Ronaldinho to develop and fine tune their skills from an early age.

Beach soccer- Playing football on the beach has been a favourite pastime of South Americans for many years. But in the early 90s, a move was made to actually turn it into a professional game. The first official pro tournament kicked

off in 1992 in Rio de Janeiro and featured stars such as Eric Cantona, Romário, Júnior and Zico. A number of tournaments are held each year since, often taking place on a beach or on some form of sand. The game is undoubtedly fun but it requires its players a greater degree of improvisation due to the soft surface, which increases the level of skills, agility and shooting abilities of its players.

Street Football- Taking the elements of football and Futsal, street football was primarily considered informal versions of both games. But like Futsal, the game with its fast-paced nature started gaining prominence everywhere it was played. Organising a game was also relatively easy as all players needed was an empty space such as a car park lot to set up a fun kick-a-bout. This game, however, did spur the development of skills and it is now viewed as an important fabric of football, which is why the inaugural Street Football Championship was organised in 2006 in Berlin to uncover the best street footballers around.

Indoor Football- the game is known in some circles as arena football or minifootball and it is normally played in a walled indoor arena. The roots of the game have been traced back to North America where players moved football indoors during the cold winter months. The difference though is that the game is played on synthetic turf and the walls come into play during the game, allowing players to bounce the ball off them during play, which is why there are no throw-ins involved. The game remains a popular sport and pastime in the U.S., Canada and Mexico where regular professional leagues are held.

Swamp Football- Not all football-inspired games have gone on to appeal to the masses. Swamp Football or Swamp Soccer for instance can best be described as an acquired taste. Played in bogs or swamps, the game reportedly originated in Finland where it was said to improve endurance and build strength. Although the thought of having a kick-a-bout in a swamp sounds ludicrous to many, some have embraced the game. There are reportedly close to 300 swamp football

teams around the world and there's even a Swamp Soccer World Cup held annually each year![3].

As a conclusion It should be noted that football is very “good doctor” for our health. Playing football is a good way to get the exercise you need to be healthy. It can help lower your chances of getting some long-term health issues like heart problems, certain types of strokes, and diabetes[4]. Playing football often can improve your heart health and help you build up your stamina over time. Football is a game where you run, walk, sprint, and kick a ball. Playing sports often helps reduce symptoms of depression and stress. Doing this can help you feel more sure of yourself and better about who you are, and it can also make you less worried and nervous.

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